

WHITE PAPER

Non Conventional Architectures

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PERFORMANCE COMPUTING**

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	3
Glossary of acronyms	4
1 Introduction	5
2 Trends & Outlook	6
2.1 Data-flow architectures	6
2.1.1 Introduction to data-flow architectures	6
2.1.2 FPGA accelerators	7
2.1.3 Coarse Grain Reconfigurable Architectures.....	8
2.2 Technologies and architectures for novel types of accelerators focusing on AI and HPC.....	9
2.2.1 Introduction to AI-oriented accelerators.....	9
2.2.2 Novel types of accelerators... ..	10
2.2.3 Beyond IMC and NMC: Neuromorphic computing.....	13
2.3 Technologies and architectures for novel types of storage.....	18
2.3.1 Solutions to massive data storage	18
2.3.2 Future challenges and opportunities for massive storage	19
2.4 Chemistry-based Computing	20
2.4.1 Introduction	20
2.4.2 DNA for Computing	20
3 Post Exascale Vision	22
4 Key R&I Recommendations	23
4.1 FPGA & dataflow Architectures recommendations:.....	23
4.2 In-memory and near-memory (IMC and NMC) computing recommendations:	23
4.3 Neuromorphic Computing recommendations:.....	23
4.4 Massive archival storage recommendations:.....	24
4.5 DNA Computing recommendations:	24
5 Conclusions	25
6 Contributing Authors (alphabetical order)	26
6.1 Acknowledgements.....	26
7 References	27

Executive Summary

This is a white paper released as part of the ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda 6.

This document offers the reader an updated view of the most promising technologies and architectures that the research community and industrial sector are underway to explore, to continue pushing compute capabilities far beyond the Exascale. This path comes with well-defined challenges (both from the hardware and software perspective) that research and industrial communities are facing, and that demand for new investments.

The level of maturity of the various technologies and non-conventional architectures is of course not the same; some are closer to a successful commercialization, others made their appearance in just laboratories. The following sections cover all the aspects involved in the implementation and integration of a new computer system. As such, we reviewed technologies and architectures (FPGAs and specialized compute engines, AI accelerators, In-memory computing, low-cost storage technologies, etc.) that we expect to see in the near future as part of upcoming supercomputers, still keeping an eye on long term disruptive ones (e.g., DNA computing).

Being aware of the big role of AI in pushing the demand for novel and energy efficient systems, our discussion follows more closely the relationship between overviewed technologies and approaches (e.g., AI accelerators, neuromorphic architectures, dataflow architectures, reduced precision, training vs inference) and the AI domain.

Glossary of acronyms

AI - Artificial Intelligence

ASIC - Application-Specific Integrated Circuit

CGRA - Coarse-Grain Reconfigurable Architectures

CPU - Central Processing Unit

CMOS - Complementary Metal-Oxide Semiconductor

CXL - Compute Express Link

DL - Deep Learning

DNN - Deep Neural Network

DRAM - Dynamic Random Access Memory

FeRAM - Ferroelectric Random Access Memory

FPGA - Field Programmable Gate Array

GPU - Graphical Processing Unit

HBM - High Bandwidth Memory

HPC - High Performance Computing

IMC - In-Memory Computing

IPU - Intelligence Processing Unit

LLM - Large Language Model

LPU - Language Processing Unit

MAC - Multiply And Accumulate

ML - Machine Learning

MPI - Message Passing Interface

NMC - Near-Memory Computing

PCIe - Peripheral Component Interconnect Express

PCM - Phase-Change Memory

PIM - Processing In Memory

RDMA - Remote Direct Memory Access

RDU - Reconfigurable Data Unit

RoCE - RDMA over Converged Ethernet

RRAM - Resistive Random Access Memory

SmartNIC - Smart Network Interface Card

SNN - Spiking Neural Networks

SRAM - Static Random Access Memory

TPU - Tensor Processing Unit

UALink - Ultra Accelerator Link

VHDL - Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language

WSE - Wafer-Scale Engine

1 Introduction

In the "Beyond Moore's Law" era, computing embracing non-conventional approaches will become increasingly prevalent. These approaches have advantages over traditional computing based on von Neumann architectures.

Several shortcomings plague current computational models and their underlying technologies. Exorbitant energy costs drain resources and will ultimately affect our environment. Challenges in reconciling fast-changing data needs with long memory retention are coming about where conventional computing systems face a trade-off between memory speed and capacity owing to hierarchical memory structures, which would have adverse consequences for a world that is always hungry for new data. There are also problems with limited parallelism - while conventional computing can achieve some parallelism through multi-core processors, not all computing tasks can be efficiently parallelized, leading to slow data processing. The von Neumann bottleneck indeed limits the size, weight and power of our current computational technologies.

As the computational requirements for artificial intelligence grow much faster than Moore's Law for electronics, more non-conventional approaches to computing and signal processing are required because of the benefits they provide in terms of energy cost, computational speed, reduced footprint, cyber resilience, and processing power. Non-conventional approaches are a very fertile field, where there isn't a single dominant technology.

AI and HPC workloads continue to push the limits of computing devices. In recent years, we have seen developers harness the compute capability of accelerators in order to meet the demands of their applications. In most cases, GPUs have been the accelerators of choice, owing to their high floating point compute capacity and high memory bandwidth. The leap from general HPC using CPUs, to GPUs has been beneficial for a large subset of applications that

could make use of the new hardware. However, being able to further specialize an implementation to the unique requirements of the application can bring substantial benefits in terms of performance and efficiency. We must look to an alternative paradigm to achieve this goal.

Within a holistic approach, the goal of this chapter is to provide an overview of the most current non-conventional technologies and highlighting the potential impacts of future developments.

2 Trends & Outlook

2.1 Data-flow architectures

2.1.1 Introduction to data-flow architectures

Data-flow architectures find their roots in the mid 70s already. Basically, dataflow machines operate on the principle of moving data through operational units rather than operations being carried out on data fetched from memory. We can distinguish between static dataflow where data moves in a predetermined fashion and without any data-dependent variations, and dynamic dataflow where computation is triggered by the arrival of data, i.e., the activation of functional units is triggered by the fulfilment of all input data. Over the past decades, this approach has been explored a lot, although a real and wide commercial success never arrived, apart from a few notable examples that are FPGAs, which implement a static form of dataflow, and out-of-order processors which implement a dynamic form of dataflow.

In traditional non-dataflow architectures, the continuous growth in the performance gap between processing speed and memory access latencies, have led to the creation of complex hierarchies of memories, forcing programmers to deeply understand their functionality in order to optimize data placement, as well as programming models to introduce complex mechanisms of synchronization. On the contrary, data-flow architectures allow the user to

describe both the way data should be processed and moved across the functional units. This makes reasoning about performance and optimizations much simpler.

The interest in data-flow architectures regained from the recent explosion of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) algorithms, where the processing flow clearly demands for data-triggered hardware support, and for a more explicit programming of data movement. Furthermore, the continuous growth of model sizes means that many ML/DL models can no longer compute on a single chip and need to be split across multiple ones. This increases the importance of dataflow models of compute that can also orchestrate the movement of data between chips, rather than just within the chip. ML/DL applications have propelled the emergence of ‘spatial computing’ architectures, where applications are transformed into execution (data-flow) graphs, which are then intelligently mapped on the hardware fabric, as shown in Figure 1 below. The capability of these architectures to extract parallelism (with a large degree of energy efficiency) is counterbalanced by the challenge of finding an optimal mapping of the compute graph onto the hardware resources. Thus, the ability of efficiently exploiting compute resources leaves the door open to the research activity. Innovative heuristics can be used in the compilation tools to maximize performance, throughput and energy consumption.

Figure 1 - Example of a dataflow-based implementation.

Also, software demands can go outside the boundaries of the compilation tools, touching the definition of programming models that better allow to express application parallelism without limiting the compilers to discover it. Remarkably, commercial examples of such architectures are facing the market (Groq [Abts 2020], SambaNova [Emani 2021], NextSilicon¹, HyperionCore²); however, the ultimate ‘universal’ solution is still far away.

2.1.2 FPGA accelerators

Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) enable users to specialize their application beyond that of GPU accelerators to create custom hardware accelerators. FPGAs are programmable hardware and do not feature a conventional instruction set architecture that executes

software; instead, they contain programmable logic blocks, memories and math units that can be used to create a specific accelerator circuit from scratch. The user’s design may constitute anything from a fully-fledged processor down to a specific acceleration kernel. The device can also be reconfigured to accelerate another task at runtime, hence “field programmable”.

At the same time, the higher programming effort needed for creating FPGA accelerators has hindered the widespread adoption of FPGAs as application accelerators. The extreme flexibility of FPGAs, their key strength as a computational device turns into a disadvantage during the programming and development phase. Traditionally, low-level hardware description languages such as VHDL and Verilog have been used to program FPGAs. These are unsuitable for most software application developers. High-

¹ <https://www.nextsilicon.com>

² <https://www.hyperion-core.com>

level synthesis tools such as AMD's Vitis tool suite provide FPGA programming from higher-level languages such as C/C++, but an underlying knowledge of hardware design is still required for performant outcomes. Dataflow programming models (e.g. MaxCompiler [Becker 2015]) have been proposed for FPGA programming, as they raise the abstraction level over low-level hardware design and provide a model that is both approachable to developers and very suitable for expressing high performing FPGA designs.

Highly customizable number formats is one the key benefits of using FPGAs as accelerators. It is possible to use almost arbitrary integer, fixed point or floating-point number formats, and by tweaking the chosen number formats to the unique requirements of the application, significant efficiency gains in terms of both performance and power efficiency can be achieved. At the same time, optimizing for custom number formats requires the developer to analyse and understand the numerical behaviour and requirements of the accelerated algorithm through the various stages of the computation, which is by no means trivial. Some tools have been developed that support the developer in exploring these custom number formats and simulating the behaviour in high level software first. With the emergence of lower precision computation in AI oriented accelerators, exploring custom number formats will become much more common in the near future. Further research and tool support will be needed to help developers explore the use of lower precision computations in their applications.

2.1.3 Coarse Grain Reconfigurable Architectures

Coarse Grain Reconfigurable Architectures (CGRAs) are, similarly to FPGAs, reconfigurable devices but computing resources are organized into larger blocks or tiles, such as processing elements and memories with higher data granularities (e.g. 8-64 bits). Similar to FPGA, CGRAs can leverage specialization as a key benefit by allowing users to create highly tuned implementations exploiting specialized cores in the case of CGRAs.

CGRAs such as AMD's AI Engine provide specialized vector instructions for processing real and complex data of various numerical data types. The devices themselves are composed of an array of compute and memory tiles connected via a network on chip (NoC). These devices are programmed with a C like language.

The advantages of both FPGAs and CGRAs are increased performance and efficiency through specialization that can be reconfigured. To exploit these devices, investment in building an HPC/AI ecosystem of libraries and tools is needed.

Modern SmartNICs are often based on CGRAs/FPGAs and differ from previous network offload devices in the extent of their programmability. It is possible for example to implement fully customized operations such as MPI collectives on arbitrary data formats as required by the application. SmartNICs enable computation within the network interface cards. This may take the form of low-level protocol acceleration or high-level functions such as MPI collective operation offload, freeing up other devices such as CPUs and GPUs to execute tasks more suited to their architectures, but research and evaluation of how applications map to infrastructures built with components such as SmartNICs remains.

2.2 Technologies and architectures for novel types of accelerators focusing on AI and HPC

2.2.1 Introduction to AI-oriented accelerators

With the recent growth of AI-oriented applications and workloads, the industry has brought forward several new architectures that are specifically targeted at accelerating AI-related computations. Demand for AI computations is driven by many applications including data analytics, computer vision, speech to text, translation and more recently large language models. AI related computations can be distinguished into training and inference phases, where training is often very compute intensive and involves very large data sets. However, training is only performed occasionally. After training has been completed, inference will be carried out on the trained model. Inference itself is less computationally demanding than training but since inference will be carried out millions or billions of times as user queries as submitted to the deployed model and responses will often be required with high throughput and low latency, inference is now expected to become the key computational challenge for AI. The widespread introduction of services built around natural language processing, image recognition, or other forms of AI inference means that deploying AI on conventional CPUs or GPUs is no longer going to be cost effective.

Many of the newly introduced AI architectures are focussed on efficient tensor (i.e. matrix) operations. When specializing in inference, lower precision numerical operations are often used. Another important aspect for inference is low batch performance to provide fast responses to queries. Here, GPUs typically struggle as they require strong batching to deliver high computational performance.

The Google **Tensor Processing Unit (TPU)** was one of the first AI accelerators introduced to

the market. TPUs support both training and inference and are very efficient for computing models with very large batch sizes. TPUs are only available through Google's internal services.

Groq³ recently launched the **Language Processing Unit (LPU)**, an AI accelerator chip specifically aimed at language processing and AI inference more generally. The LPU executes in a static dataflow model and achieves low batch performance by using only on-chip SRAM as memory. Scalability for larger scale applications is achieved by using chip-to-chip interconnect such that models can be split across several chips without becoming bottlenecked by PCIe interconnect.

Graphcore⁴ offers the **Intelligence Processing Unit (IPU)**, a massively parallel architecture with many small processor cores and local memory, which is efficient at executing fine-grain threads with irregular behaviour. The IPU is conceptually closer to a conventional multi-core processor but provides more parallelism than CPUs and is more efficient at irregular workloads than GPUs.

Sambanova⁵ offers a **Reconfigurable Dataflow Unit (RDU)** which is a CGRA architecture composed of memory and processing units. It uses a spatial programming model and, as all dataflow architectures, aims to minimize data transfers between computations.

Cerebras⁶ has developed the **Wafer Scale Engine (WSE)**, a single, wafer-scale processor that includes compute, memory and interconnect. Processor cores are optimized for sparse linear algebra. The entire architecture is optimized on system level rather than adding PCIe cards to conventional servers. Cerebras released their CS-3 system featuring a very large number of cores, on-chip SRAM, and bandwidth.

The above demonstrates there is significant innovation in architecture, driven by demand in novel AI-based applications. At the same time, this plethora of new architectures raises the question of how they can be effectively

³ <https://groq.com>

⁴ <https://www.graphcore.ai>

⁵ <https://sambanova.ai>

⁶ <https://cerebras.net>

programmed and used in a range of application areas. While many of these architectures are provided with tooling that are based on AI oriented frameworks around TensorFlow and PyTorch, it is less clear how these architectures could be used in other areas outside of AI such as classical HPC. While high compute performance for tensor operations seems suitable for solving more general linear algebra problems, the programming and integration in non-AI applications will require further research. Further areas of investigation are whether training and inference can be effectively addressed by a unified architecture or if they are better addressed by more specialized approaches, or how AI-oriented algorithms such as graph neural networks or transformer models can be used to augment classical simulations.

For some time, AI and HPC architectures have been converging on various fronts, such as using the same accelerators (in many cases GPU-based) whether the final aim is to do supercomputing (which requires double precision floating point) or to do training of CNN networks (which used to require single precision floating point). This helped system integrators to build products that could be utilized in the datacentre or supercomputing deployments. However, this is a very fluid and changing space; for example, with the Blackwell GPU from NVIDIA that has forsaken double-precision floating point and instead proposed a new very-narrow 4-bit Floating Point (FP4) support in hardware. While FP4 seems well-suited for LLMs, classic HPC applications will not benefit from this.

There is also consolidation with open interconnect technologies towards a flexible and high performant AI and HPC infrastructure. With Computer Express Link (CXL) and Ultra Accelerator Link (UALink), two technologies for efficient CPU-to-memory and CPU-to-device communication are being standardized. Ultra Ethernet aims at efficient node-to-node communication, providing RDMA semantics and message passing at a very large scale. It will compete with and potentially replace RoCE and InfiniBand technologies in the data centre. As open standards to be supported by many vendors, these technologies will benefit both AI and HPC workloads thanks to economies of scale.

2.2.2 Novel types of accelerators

The traditional von Neumann computing architecture incurs a growing overhead in latency and energy with data-intensive applications, as more and more operands and results have to be transferred between processor and memory (also known as the memory wall). It is imperative to explore new emerging computing paradigms that are robust, adaptive, and energy efficient.

The most energy-efficient implementations of operations that require intensive access to a large number of parameters, such as DNNs and LLMs, are specialized architectures that can overcome the von Neumann bottleneck, by not moving the parameters, such as the synaptic weights, for each operation to be performed, and produce highly efficient vector-matrix products using multiply-and-accumulate (MAC) operations, which are the core of the computation of neural networks but also other scientific computing primitives. Accelerators that perform the MAC operations directly inside the memory unit, where the parameters are stored, provide such an opportunity to achieve high parallelism and outstanding performance, which result in high-energy efficiency and low latency solutions. Memory cells based on embedded non-volatile memories or more mature memories like SRAM can be used to store the synaptic weights and perform the MAC operation by means of Ohm's law and Kirchhoff's law.

From a hardware design perspective, despite the maturity of the silicon manufacturing technology behind some of the solutions proposed in literature, there are still several challenges that have to be addressed in order to make this computing paradigm of benefit for many applications, and widely adopted. Looking at the SRAM technology, the advantage is undoubtedly brought by the manufacturing process that scaled down constantly in the last decades. SRAM storage cells are quite simple, as they are made of two chained inverters closed in a loop. Despite the simplicity of the design, which offers room for implementing both Boolean logic operations, as well as other arithmetic operations, some criticalities exist. The cell is more sensitive to operations that require multiple rows to be activated in parallel, which may lead

to destruction of the content of some cells. Different designs based on 8T, 10T and even using more transistors, improve the operation's reliability, but at the expense of a larger area consumption. Even worse is the case of using the cells in their analog regime, since the sensitivity to manufacturing process variations, unbalancing of the sense amplifiers, and the need of conversion circuitry to/from the analog/digital domains make this a large area consuming approach. Indeed, applications that require storing and processing large amounts of data (e.g., AI models) are greatly hindered. For instance, such applications imply that multiple rows are activated in parallel, leading to large currents being driven on shared bitlines; such currents strongly influence other cells not involved in the computations, as well they lead to accelerated aging, power consumption and thermal issues.

DRAM-based designs can get advantage from the relatively small area of a single cell; however, the intrinsic dynamic nature of the cells quickly challenges the designers. Cells are very sensitive to changes of the charge accumulated in the smaller capacitors. The access to the cell content is a destructive operation per se, requiring additional circuitry to be restored. The higher sensitivity due to the presence of single line sense amplifiers makes the cells more prone to errors.

Alternative forms of storing information, such as phase-change memory (PCM), resistive RAM (RRAM), ferroelectric RAM (FeRAM) and others are promising technologies, since they try to combine non volatility with relative high access speed. The great challenges that come with designs based on these technologies are essentially i) the non trivial integration with traditional CMOS technology processing, and ii) their relatively low density. Especially when used in the analog domain, these technologies suffer from the problem of requiring additional conversion circuitry.

Solutions for custom digital accelerators, in-memory computing (IMC) and near-memory processing (NMC)

The most mature and active area is that of building custom digital accelerators. The main ideas being tried out are reduced precision arithmetic, complex instructions (eg. Tensor operations), very good data locality, etc. The research on custom digital accelerators is likely to continue with further innovations such as 3D stacked memory, support for efficient fine-tuning, etc.

In the domain of IMC-based accelerators, the primary players are Axelera AI⁷, EnCharge AI⁸ and d-Matrix⁹. All of them perform IMC using SRAM (either digital or mixed-signal). Companies such as STMicroelectronics have also published neural processing units based on IMC using SRAM. Compared to IMC with SRAM, IMC with embedded non-volatile memory such as phase-change memory is at an earlier stage of development. The potential for higher weight capacity and non-volatility is the primary motivation for IMC with PCM. ST Microelectronics is also working closely with IBM on developing NPUs based on embedded phase-change memory, with support from Horizon Europe¹⁰, illustrated in Figure 2 below.

⁷ <https://www.axelera.ai/>

⁸ <https://www.enchargeai.com/>

⁹ <https://www.d-matrix.ai/etc>

¹⁰ <https://neurosoc.eu/>

Figure 2 - High-level Design view of the NeuroSoC system, incorporating a cluster of PCM analog with in-memory computing tiles (AIMC), SRAM local storage units (LSUs), specialized digital processing units (DPUs), and a RISC-V co-processor. Source: <https://neurosoc.eu/>

Besides IMC, the related area of near-memory computing (NMC), which also falls under the broad umbrella of processing in memory (PIM), is gaining a lot of traction. Much of the NMC activity is tied to DRAM technology. Samsung and AMD developed the MI100 with HBM-PIM¹¹. SK Hynix is also actively developing PIM-based solutions such as the AiM-centric accelerator card¹².

UPMEM¹³ PIM is another example of a PIM product based on DRAM chips augmented with a RISC-like proprietary processor placed close to the data array. It acts as a conventional

accelerator, allowing to offload the main CPU from performing specific computations. Zero-Point¹⁴ can be considered as a form of specialized NMC too, where on-the-fly data compression and defragmentation are transparently applied to the memory transactions.

For a most recent and comprehensive review of the research and commercial landscape of this family of technologies, see [Khan 2024]. For a roadmap to neuromorphic computing, that encompasses IMC as well, see [Mehonic 2024].

¹¹ <https://semiconductor.samsung.com/news-events/tech-blog/hbm-pim-cutting-edge-memory-technology-to-accelerate-next-generation-ai/>

¹² <https://news.skhynix.com/sk-hynix-debuts-first-gddr6-aim-accelerator-card-aimx-for-generative-ai/>

¹³ <https://www.upmem.com>

¹⁴ <https://www.zeropoint-tech.com>

Future challenges and opportunities

PIM solutions either with IMC or NMC could have a dramatic impact on the AI acceleration landscape. It is foreseeable that even 3D non-volatile memory technology such as NAND and NOR Flash could be leveraged for PIM with the potential for dense, highly energy efficient, low cost, and instant ON inference accelerators. IMC with 3D non-volatile memory is at an early stage of development and is being supported by funding agencies such as DARPA through the DARPA OPTIMA program.

Despite the above-mentioned progresses and some few commercial solutions, more challenges still exist, especially on the software side. Indeed, programming models still rely on conventional approaches that are not able to fully capture the potential benefit of moving computation close to the memory rather than the opposite. Also, compilers need to integrate more abstractions in order to transparently expose such kinds of accelerators to the application level, including an optimal abstraction of the type of operations that can be executed (Boolean functions, arithmetic operations even on floating point numbers, convolutions, pattern matching, etc.). In this sense, the rise of RISC-V architectures opened the doors to a more convenient way of creating such an interface, by fully exploiting customization of the ISA at first. More and more designs based on RISC-V custom instructions are on the horizon.

2.2.3 Beyond IMC and NMC: Neuromorphic computing

Despite its relatively modest dimensions, the human brain exhibits a computational complexity that has long inspired the development of computing systems that mimic its capabilities. Unlike conventional analog/digital computers, the brain employs a combination of analog computation and digital communication via spikes to enhance its resilience to noise. This distinctive computational method, evolved over millions of years in animal species, represents a novel paradigm that is only recently being explored for computation purposes.

The brain, with its particular characteristics of energy efficiency, fault tolerance, and ability to self-organize based on environmental inputs, offers valuable inspiration on how to achieve these goals. Now is the ideal time to use what we know about how the brain computes to develop efficient, brain-inspired computing solutions [Urgese 2023]. To address the well-known limitations of the von Neumann architecture, several solutions have been proposed, including the development of neuromorphic systems inspired by neuroscience and biology. Neuromorphic systems are optimized to simulate spiking neural networks (SNNs)—characterized by sparse and asynchronous internal activity—which emulate the dynamics of networks of neurons observed in animal brains, as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3 - An analogy between **a.** the brain and **b.** a neuromorphic computing system with spiking neurons. The neurons in the brain communicate via spikes of voltage that are sparse (rare) in space and in time, yielding very high efficiency. Relative spike timing can accurately communicate a wide range of values, from high (early spikes for bright light) to low (late spikes for dark light). Neuromorphic systems leverage these principles for efficient computing. Analogy of brain and neuromorphic computing with spiking neural networks. Note: source: IBM

The concept of neuromorphic engineering was initially proposed by Carver Mead in the late 1980s, with the objective of emulating the structural and functional characteristics of biological nervous systems. With the advent and diffusion of ANN-based solutions, neuromorphic computing has gained significant attention for its energy efficiency, robustness, and computational speed. In contrast to the conventional architecture, which is vulnerable to latency and high power consumption due to extensive data transfers, neuromorphic systems

employ an asynchronous, event-driven computing paradigm.

Neuromorphic architectures are optimized for the simulation of spiking neurons that process sparse input events and remain inactive without input, as opposed to the continuous signal processing in traditional ANNs, as detailed in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4 - Illustrations of the parallels between (a) the spiking and artificial neurons, (b) the SNNs and ANNs

Neuromorphic devices employ digital, analog, or mixed VLSI circuits to create artificial neurons and synapses that efficiently emulate the biological behaviours observed in the human brain. For this purpose, various materials, including ferroelectric transistors and memristors, have been introduced for the development of neuromorphic devices. The applications of neuromorphic devices are diverse, spanning scientific research and practical tasks such as classification, regression, control, and many others. These systems are utilized in two primary categories of applications: scientific applications aiming to simulate and understand human brain behaviour, thereby advancing neuroscience [Patton 2022]; and practical applications such as image and speech recognition, autonomous robotics, and medical devices, where neuromorphic computing excels at enabling fast, energy-efficient decision-making and real-time processing of sensor data [Schuman 2022].

Solutions for neuromorphic computing

Over the past 15 years, several large-scale neuromorphic systems have been developed by different research teams. Since 1998, the Advanced Processor Technologies Research Group at the University of Manchester has been engaged in the development of SpiNNaker, a digital globally asynchronous locally synchronous neuromorphic supercomputer, which successfully simulated one million neurons by 2018. Between 2011 and 2015, the University of Heidelberg team developed the BrainScaleS system, a hybrid wafer-scale analog neuromorphic supercomputer. Both projects were funded by the European Union's Human Brain Project¹⁵, which was established with the objective of facilitating brain simulations for neuroscience research and to explore the potential applications of a brain-inspired computing paradigm deployable on the neuromorphic architectures. The aforementioned two neuromorphic systems, along with all other products developed

¹⁵ <https://www.humanbrainproject.eu/en/science-development/focus-areas/neuromorphic-computing/hardware/>

within the HBP project, are accessible on the Ebrains platform¹⁶. This platform will undergo further extension to provide support for new tools and resources, employing a service-oriented paradigm that will be suitable for both research and enterprise users.

In 2019, researchers at Tsinghua University introduced Tianjic, a versatile chip that supports both spiking and traditional neural networks. The chip was demonstrated in a self-driving bicycle that was capable of obstacle avoidance, autonomous navigation, and responding to voice commands. Large companies such as IBM and Intel have also been active in this field; IBM released TrueNorth in 2014, and Intel released Loihi in 2017, followed by its successor Loihi2 in 2021, which offers enhanced capabilities and supports different neuron models, and powers Hala Point, the first large-scale neuromorphic system to demonstrate state-of-the-art computational efficiencies on mainstream AI workloads¹⁷. DYNAP-SE2, developed by the Institute of Neuroinformatics at UZH and ETH Zurich, is a mixed-signal chip with analog spiking neurons and synapses.

In addition to the development of custom-designed neuromorphic systems, several research teams have created FPGA-deployable neuromorphic architectures with the objective of providing computer science researchers with access to neuromorphic hardware that may otherwise be limited. These architectures offer

researchers flexibility in programming the architecture to suit different use cases and experiments. Researchers can rapidly iterate on different neuron and synapse models, learning rules, and network topologies without needing to deploy a new hardware design for each change.

To support the development of neuromorphic applications, several frameworks have been developed by academy and industry efforts. One notable example is the Nengo framework¹⁸, a Python tool for building functional brain models that have been used to implement SNNs for deep learning, vision, motor control, working memory, attractor dynamics, inductive reasoning, path integration, and planning with problem solving. Another recent initiative is represented by the Intel Lava software framework¹⁹, an open-source, modular, and extensible platform designed for creating neuro-inspired applications and mapping them to neuromorphic hardware. Its platform-agnostic nature allows applications to be prototyped on conventional CPUs and GPUs before being deployed to diverse system architectures, including both traditional processors and neuromorphic chips.

Moreover, a number of software tools have been accelerated on GPUs, including GeNN²⁰, NEURON²¹, NEST²², Brian²³, snnTorch²⁴, SpikingJelly²⁵, Rockpool²⁶. These tools have contributed to the advancement of the field, enabling large communities of neuroscientists and AI designers to configure, train, and simulate SNN models in widely recognized frameworks.

Recently, several companies have entered the field with commercial products. Xylo²⁷, introduced by SynSense in 2023, is a fully digital neuromorphic chip designed to process low-dimensional input signals. SynSense also produced the Speck²⁸ chip, a fully event-driven

¹⁶ <https://www.ebrains.eu/brain-atlases/computing-132/neuromorphic-computing-324>

¹⁷ <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/newsroom/news/intel-builds-worlds-largest-neuromorphic-system.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.nengo.ai/>

¹⁹ <https://lava-nc.org/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/genn-team/genn>

²¹ <https://nrn.readthedocs.io>

²² <https://www.nest-simulator.org/>

²³ <https://briansimulator.org/>

²⁴ <https://snntorch.readthedocs.io/>

²⁵ <https://github.com/fangwei123456/spikingjelly>

²⁶ <https://rockpool.ai/>

²⁷ <https://www.synsense.ai/products/xylo>

²⁸ <https://www.synsense.ai/products/speck-2>

neuromorphic vision SoC capable of supporting spiking convolutional neural networks (sCNN) with a fully asynchronous chip architecture. Brainchip launched the digital neuromorphic processor IP called Akida²⁹ in 2021, which is designed as a brain-inspired device capable of analyzing only essential sensor inputs at the point of acquisition to process data with unprecedented performance, precision, and reduced power consumption. SpiNNcloud³⁰ Systems company has recently made the official launch of the SpiNNaker2 platform, a multi-chip system designed to simulate SNNs applicable to AI and optimization tasks. The architecture of the SpiNNaker2 platform is based on a low-power mesh of 152 ARM-based cores, which support high-speed, power-proportional interconnection essential for scaling and communicating across multiple chips. Thus, enhancing the ability to deploy large-scale distributed neural networks. Moreover, the chip incorporates native accelerators that have been designed with neuromorphic computing tasks in mind.

For a most recent and comprehensive review of the research and commercial landscape of neuromorphic software and hardware technologies, refer to Open Neuromorphic³¹, a neuromorphic computing and engineering community-maintained online resource. A recent and comprehensive review paper on the topic of neuromorphic computing and spiking neural networks is [Rahti 2023].

Future challenges and opportunities for neuromorphic computing

Neuromorphic computing faces significant challenges, including programming complexity, compatibility with the available software ecosystem of libraries and languages, and hardware constraints [Christensen 2022]. In the current landscape, all of these lead to different development paces between software and hardware and among different organizations, either academic or industrial. To face such fragmentation, the Neuromorphic Intermediate Representation (NIR) [Pedersen 2023] has been

recently proposed: a platform-independent set of continuous-time computational primitives that improves interoperability by simplified translation of computational graphs.

A complementary effort towards standardization is represented by NeuroBench [Yik 2024], a suite of benchmarks explicitly intended for neuromorphic computing at the system level as well as at the algorithmic level.

Moreover, training SNNs can be very challenging compared to their traditional counterparts. This is due to the non-differentiable nature of spiking neurons, which makes the standard backpropagation algorithm inapplicable. To address these challenges several methods have been proposed. One such method is training ANNs with continuous inputs before converting them to SNNs, with equivalent accuracy for temporally-coded SNNs [Stanojevic 2023]. Another method approximates spiking activation functions for backpropagation and trains them like ANNs enabling even better results [Wozniak 2020]. Still backpropagation-based training is computationally intensive and unsuitable for efficient on-chip learning. Alternatively, supervised online learning through forward error propagation is possible [Bohnstingl 2022], or unsupervised learning techniques such as spike-timing-dependent plasticity, which adjust synaptic weights based on spike-timing correlations. Despite enormous progress, neuromorphic computing still has several challenges outlined above that restrict the general applicability of neuromorphic devices and algorithms, rendering them currently more suitable for specific, low-complexity tasks where their advantages can be fully exploited. Future research and development efforts across hardware and algorithms has the potential to enable efficient AI solutions based on neuromorphic computing.

²⁹ <https://brainchip.com/akida-neural-processor-soc>

³⁰ <https://spinncloud.com/>

³¹ <https://open-neuromorphic.org/>

2.3 Technologies and architectures for novel types of storage

2.3.1 Solutions to massive data storage

The continued exponential growth of data combined with the slow-down in the areal density and capacity scaling of hard disk drives is driving an urgent need for innovation in storage systems. The combination of these trends is leading to unsustainable increases in storage costs and the associated power consumption and CO2 footprint.

Fortunately, a large fraction of the data currently residing on HDD is cold data, i.e. it is infrequently accessed, and in some cases, never accessed but must be kept for legal compliance

or is kept for its potential future value. The financial and environmental cost of storing such data could be significantly reduced by moving it to a lower cost / lower power storage tier in a hierarchical storage system. For example, current magnetic tape systems offer much lower total cost of ownership and a reduction in power and CO2 footprint that are both more than 90% lower compared to HDD based storage. However, tape systems have a much higher access latency and hence not all data is suitable for migration, depending on the anticipated future access patterns. Beyond its current benefits, the areal density and capacity of tape systems is also projected to continue scaling from current state of the art native capacities of up to 50TB to hundreds of TB's within the next decade, as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5 - Past and projected evolution of areal storage density for HDD and tape. Source: <https://insic.org/>

There are also a variety of emerging technologies under development to reduce the cost and environmental impact of archiving data, including Cerabyte³² in Germany and 5D memory Crystal³³ in the UK. In the longer term, DNA based data storage has the potential for even higher volumetric storage efficiency.

2.3.2 Future challenges and opportunities for massive storage

There are two significant barriers to moving data to a more efficient archival tier such as tape or one of the emerging technologies in the future. The first is knowing what data is cold and can be moved to a lower tier without impacting performance. Many organizations have tens to hundreds of PBs of data and billions of files with both metrics growing exponentially. Hence there is a need for research in the use of AI technology to analyse the data and provide recommendations for data that is suitable for migration and eventually to automate the migration process.

Another challenge for many organizations and in particular, for large science and supercomputing centres, is the integration of an archival tier into existing storage and compute infrastructure. Object storage and the S3 protocol are emerging as de facto industry standards for such applications and there are a variety of archival cloud storage and commercial software offerings that support S3 object storage. The development of open-source software with an S3 interface that supports the use of high latency media such as tape and/or the emerging technologies discussed above will enable a much broader adoption of cold archival storage tiers. Research in these areas could leverage and build on the work done previously on hierarchical storage management for exascale compute in the SAGE, SAGE2 and IO-SEA EU research projects.

DNA, as a storage medium, has significant advantages [Cao 2022]: modern storage systems face the problems of high cost and high energy consumption, and DNA has captured the attention of researchers as a storage medium due to

its high parallelism, low maintenance cost, and great storage potential resulting from its base-pair structure. DNA also offers many unique potential advantages, such as stability lasting decades or even centuries, compared to traditional media that need frequent updates. Molecular biology methods facilitate easy replication, preventing degradation and ensuring data integrity over time. Researchers have successfully encoded text, images, and JavaScript programs into DNA sequences, demonstrating its potential for versatile data storage. Recent proposals for DNA storage systems, however, are still confronted with some obstacles: (i) The real storage density in systems currently in use is less than the high theoretical storage density of DNA. (ii) Mistakes are common in DNA synthesis and sequencing, requiring duplicate data to be added for mistake correction or more sequencing coverage and double-end reads to ensure data consistency, which raises expenses. (iii) While earlier coding innovations have proven successful in particular contexts, there hasn't been a cohesive system-wide strategy, which has resulted in coordination errors between different coding locations, disconnections across encoding outcomes, and inadequate system coupling overall.

³² <https://www.cerabyte.com/>

³³ <https://www.5dmemorycrystal.com>

2.4 Chemistry-based Computing

2.4.1 Introduction

A widely used form of computation using chemistry is based on biomolecules such as DNA.

Another branch of chemical computing tries to exploit simpler molecules, through the complex and non-linear nature of oscillatory chemical reactions [Dueñas-Díez, 2019]. Ever since the introduction and first modelling by Belousov and Zhabotinsky, their reaction has been used to understand periodic or cyclic behaviours in living systems. Extensive investigations resulted in detailed kinetic mechanisms and other examples of oscillatory reactions were produced.

2.4.2 DNA for Computing

DNA computing [Kumar 2022], [Gangadharan 2021] is an innovative technology that combines computer science with molecular biology, and uses the natural parallelism of DNA structures to solve complex problems that go beyond traditional computers. Unlike silicon-based computers, DNA computing encodes data using genetic bases and relies on in-solution chemical reactions to perform calculations, guided by predefined rules that govern DNA's interactions with other biological and environmental factors [Wang 2023]. This distinction offers unique advantages and challenges for the development of DNA computing. Its key advantages include low energy use and parallel processing, allowing DNA to process multiple strands simultaneously, improving speed over traditional sequential computers. Initially designed to solve mathematical problems like SAT and maximum clique, DNA computing explores all possible outcomes simultaneously due to

the stochastic nature of molecular interactions, though it is limited by molecule availability and problem size [Inside 2024].

Recent advances in genetics had a significant impact on DNA editing, particularly with the emergence of technologies such as CRISPR-Cas9 [Ansori 2023]. CRISPR-Cas9, where CRISPR stands for "Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats" and Cas9 refers to "CRISPR-associated protein 9", is a powerful gene editing tool that uses a guide Ribonucleic acid (RNA) to target specific DNA sequences and the enzyme Cas9 to cut them, enabling precise genetic modifications. This technology, represented in Figure 6 below, has proven versatile in various applications, including bioengineering and bioinformatics. In particular, CRISPR-Cas9 has been used to store data in DNA [Sadremomtaz 2023], encode images in bacterial genomes [Shipman 2017] and perform bitwise calculations with user-defined inputs [Kim 2019]. Overall, CRISPR-Cas9 offers a wide range of applications and transformative potential for DNA computing.

Figure 6 -Representation of the CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing tool. The figure shows the key components of this technology, namely the single guide RNA, which acts as a molecular guide, the Cas9 protein, which acts as a molecular scissor, and the DNA site.

DNA computing holds great promise, but in order to reach its full potential, several challenges and limitations need to be addressed. Scalability and molecular reaction efficiency represents a major obstacle: as the number of participating DNA molecules increases, the specificity and efficiency of these reactions can deteriorate, making it difficult to scale the circuit. There are limitations also regarding speed and efficiency as well. Particularly, DNA computing is neither as fast or as efficient as conventional silicon-based computers, although it could surpass them if fully developed. Only some of the challenges of this technology have been reported here; for more detailed and in-depth reading, readers are referred to [Doricchi 2022] and [Jain 2022].

The use of DNA's unique features, including its enormous capacity for information storage and parallel processing skills, has advanced significantly in recent years, and a number of applications across different sectors have been made explicit. These include data storage, data encryption, steganography, nanotechnology, optimization, building Boolean circuits, and even quantum computing, highlighting potential to revolutionize diverse fields. However, challenges remain, and addressing these will be crucial to realize the full potential of DNA computing.

3 Post Exascale Vision

The concepts, technologies, and challenges described here will become increasingly relevant as we transition to the post-exascale era. With confidence, we can expect that heterogeneity and specialization will continue growing in terms of hardware technologies. This leads to the already-cited challenges of architecting and exploiting infrastructures of greater complexity, for which specific technical solutions will be needed. This also leads to a risk of spreading R&D investments too much across different approaches, or alternatively to focus on more familiar approaches at the expense of more disruptive ones. A proper balance will be needed across various approaches, including those covered here, such as dataflow-based, in-memory and near-memory, all the way to neuromorphic computing, and eventually adopting new models of biology or chemistry-based computing, in conjunction with various approaches to massive data storage.

4 Key R&I Recommendations

4.1 FPGA & dataflow Architectures recommendations:

- FPGAs represent a well mature technology with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) set to the highest value when considering the single devices; more challenges still exist when they have to be massively deployed (at-scale):
 - Large availability of FPGAs requires promoting their adoption in large experimental testbeds (TRLs 5-6) -e.g., dedicated experimental partitions on supercomputers.
 - Pushing the development of a more user-friendly SW ecosystem: in a fashion similar to CUDA/ROCm ecosystems for GPUs, developing libraries and SW abstractions that ease the programming task.
 - Creating and spreading out open-source (soft) cores to enable end users to develop applications around this technology.
- The growing pressing on creating of AI-focused HPC infrastructures agencies, as a mean to support the development of large AI models (e.g., Foundation Models) is a good chance for experimenting with more energy efficient architectures (static data-flow style, FPGA-based, etc.):
 - Moving to middle-high TRL for such kind of accelerated infrastructures
 - Enhancing the SW ecosystem at scale, including middleware
 - Supporting a large deployment of enhanced smartNICs and data processing units

4.2 In-memory and near-memory (IMC and NMC) computing recommendations:

- Support the development of novel hardware addressing the spectrum of needs (from edge to datacentre), extending beyond the current or soon to be commercially available (TRLs 7-9) approaches targeting edge applications, towards the higher-performance datacentre/HPC applications with the exploitation of non-volatile memories for IMC with increased density and performance, including 3D memory and heterogeneous integration (TRLs 4-6).
- Support the development of software, including programming models, compilers, etc, to optimally exploit and integrate the IMC and NMC hardware capabilities with prototype demonstrations, including integration in open ISAs such as RISC-V (TRLs 4-6)
- Promote creation and access to IMC and NMC technology through larger-scale deployments and demonstrate HPC/AI applications acceleration, fostering a European ecosystem of partners to drive innovation at all levels, from memory technology companies, accelerator technology companies, to academic and scientific users.

4.3 Neuromorphic Computing recommendations:

- Support the development of intermediate representation and compiler standards for the configuration and deployment of SNN models on heterogeneous neuromorphic platforms (TRLs 4-6). [High Priority]
- Promote the development and maintenance of multi-platform benchmarks that can be used to make fair comparisons of

available neuromorphic solutions. [Mid Priority]

- Stimulate the development of unified and standardized programming models and software frameworks to enhance interoperability and facilitate the porting of SNN models across different neuromorphic platforms. [Mid Priority]
- Currently, there is a lack of accessibility to neuromorphic HW, which is primarily available to a limited number of research teams. Only a few companies, such as SpinCloud, Brainchip, and Synsense, offer TRLs 8-9 neuromorphic platforms. To address this challenge, we have identified three strategies:
 - Promote the development of **open source HW architectures** deployable on FPGAs. [High Priority]
 - Support the development of **cloud-based prototyping platforms** hosting the major available neuromorphic architectures accessible via remote by developers. [High Priority]
 - Engage leading players in the silicon industry in the **development of neuromorphic SoC architectures**. [Low Priority]

4.4 Massive archival storage recommendations:

- Given the exploding needs of HPC and AI in terms of data, whether as input, as intermediate results, or as outputs in their workflows, there is a need to ensure a sustainable and seamless integration of current and future massive archival storage solutions, as well as promote the research for improved and/or new such storage hardware technologies spanning TRLs 4-9.
- Work previously done on hierarchical storage management for exascale compute in the SAGE, SAGE2 and IO-SEA EU research projects should be extended to account for the criticality to keep an affordable, secure, and sustainable record of quickly expanding datasets.

4.5 DNA Computing recommendations:

DNA computing, currently at TRLs 2-3, still remains in early research stages. To advance this technology beyond its experimental phase, key actions include the following points:

- **Error Correction:** Develop robust techniques to enhance DNA-based calculation reliability through improved sequencing and molecular encoding.
- **Scalability:** Address DNA computing scalability by developing strategies to control molecular interactions without causing degradation and enhance reaction specificity and efficiency.
- **Standardization:** Establish standards and integrate DNA computing with existing frameworks, fostering collaboration between biologists, computer scientists, and engineers.
- **Applications:** Focus on high-impact use cases like data storage or cryptography to demonstrate DNA computing's practicality and attract funding.
- **Gene-editing:** Explore CRISPR-Cas9 applications in bioinformatics to advance DNA computing technology.

5 Conclusions

Modern conventional computer architectures (which include compute, storage and communication aspects), mostly dominated by von Neumann ones, are struggling to provide ever more performance and showing greater energy efficiency. The AI revolution accompanied by applications generating massive volumes of data is pushing the demand for novel approaches to move, process and store data. This all poses many challenges that the research community is addressing through the proposition of non-conventional architectures and innovative technologies.

Novel technologies are coming as alternatives to InfiniBand for low latency, high speed data communication and processing. Leveraging the success of GPUs, novel specialized compute and storage architectures are emerging, while others, despite not being entirely new, (e.g., FPGAs) are gaining consensus over a wider community. This report illustrates a broad spectrum of solutions, which also include those based on less mature technologies. On the other hand, disruptive approaches like DNA computing appear to be an alternative to conventional architectures in a more distant future.

Beside the hardware aspects, the (commercial) success of new architectures is closely linked to the availability of a mature and rich software ecosystem that allows end users to focus on the high-level application development rather than on the burden of low-level programming. This includes specialized middleware and programming models, as well as coordination, monitoring and workflow description tools. For instance, high-level synthesis for FPGAs enables software developers to quickly translate their algorithms into efficient hardware structures. Similarly, the emergence of common and standardized low-level abstractions will accelerate the adoption of such non-conventional architectures at scale. Indeed, some of the

challenges coming with these solutions (e.g., neuromorphic processors) can be ascribed to a lesser extent to their deployments, which see their availability on a very small scale.

A modular approach emerged in recent years to ease the integration at scale of such novel and specialized systems (e.g., the Modular Supercomputing Architecture³⁴). This is also helping Europe in strengthening its position in the realm of AI deployment at large-scale, by funding dedicated partitions on current Peta- and pre-Exascale systems, as well by acquiring new dedicated AI supercomputers³⁵. Apart from few notable examples of large scale, fully operational services (e.g., SpiNNaker-2, BrainScaleS, or the decommissioned Project Catapult³⁶), the transition from research vehicles to well established technological pillars remains largely unexplored territory.

This document summarizes the most promising technologies and architectures foreseen having a huge impact in the coming future in the computing domain. It highlights how most of these non-conventional architectures are driven by the AI focused workloads, making the case for demanding a more structured approach to transitioning them to well-established computing platforms.

³⁴ <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/jsc/about-us/structure/divisions/technology-division/next-gen-arch-proto/msa>

³⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-factories>

³⁶ <https://tacc.utexas.edu/systems/catapult/>

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